

Book Reviews

Stephen F. Cohen, *War with Russia? From Putin and Ukraine to Trump and Russia Gate*, (New York: Hot Books Publisher, 2019), Price: INR 5,219.00, Pages: 251.

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Stephen Cohen's *War with Russia?* centers on his assessment of the situation that the new US-Russian Cold War is far more dangerous than its 40-year old predecessor, which the world barely survived. Cohen cites that during the preceding cold war, the possibility of a nuclear catastrophe was in the forefront of American mainstream political and media discussion, and in policy-making decisions and laws. The book draws attention to this new cold war, that has been evolving in Ukraine and which has been over ruled by Russiagate allegations that remain unproven. This orthodox narrative of U.S has also constrained President Trump's capacity to conduct crisis-negotiations with Moscow while American media outlets have vilified Russian President Putin for attacking "America Democracy" during the 2016 presidential campaign. Cohen's book is an excerpt of his radio broadcasts from 'The John Bachelor Show', a program based at WABC AM in New York.

In this book, Cohen states that "Cold war without diplomacy is a recipe for actual war; one that is unfolding in the heart of Russia's historic civilization." The political epicenter of the new cold war is not in far-away Berlin, as it was from the late 1940s on, but directly on Russia's borders, where NATO's unprecedented buildup continues and is provoking equally dangerous forms of Russian "brinkmanship." The Ukrainian civil war in Donbass, Moscow and Kiev, precipitated by the unlawful change of the government in Kiev is already growing into a proxy US-Russian war which can lead to an actual war between US-led NATO and post-Soviet Russia.

The Ukraine crises that erupted in 2014 have been blamed solely on the “aggression” of Putin, which Cohen considers as a highly questionable assertion but more an orthodox media narrative of the new cold war. The book delves into how demonizing Putin has generated more widespread Russiophobic hysteria among the American political and media elites rather than among ordinary American citizens; which according to Cohen is neo-McCarthyism. Cohen’s disparate view on the Russian leader has made him out to be the prominent defender of Putin. He contends that branding Putin as “kleptocrat” lacks context as Putin had mobilized enough wealth to undo and reverse those human catastrophes and put billions of dollars in rainy-day funds that buffered the nation in different hard times that lay ahead. In the book, Cohen questions that if the Russians are accused of wrongly perceiving American intentions, hasn’t Washington given them cause to do so? Putting it another way, is Putin really the “aggressor” depicted by the US political-media establishment or a leader responding to a decades-long “American war against Russia?” Due to such remarks, Cohen has been attributed as Putin’s American “apologist,” among the American media elites.

Cohen has pointed out in the book that Moscow’s view of the Ukrainian crisis is entirely missing in the ‘US mainstream’ coverage. Cohen, being an acclaimed historian of Soviet and post-Soviet Russia, explains that the underlying causes of the crisis are Ukraine’s own internal divisions and not primarily Putin’s actions. The essential factor escalating the crisis has been Kiev’s “anti-terrorist” military campaign against its own citizens, mainly in Luhansk and Donetsk. According to Cohen, the proposal by Washington and Brussels to bring Ukraine into NATO’s “sphere of influence” was a form of political aggression against the centuries of intimate relations between large segments of Ukrainian society and Russia. Ukraine is deeply divided as to whether it should join Europe or remain close politically and economically to Russia. There is not one Ukraine or one “Ukrainian people” but at least two, generally situated in its western and eastern regions. Cohen further adds that everything that followed from Russia’s annexation of Crimea and the spread of rebellion in southeastern Ukraine to the civil war and Kiev’s “anti-terrorist operation,” was triggered by the February coup, which was endorsed by Washington and Brussels.

The book progresses towards another cold war front that has become more fraught with the possibility of hot war in Syria, where the growing numbers of American troops are increasing in military proximity to the Russian-Syrian alliance. In the book, Cohen examines how the neocon/liberal interventionist principles and practices that have guided US policies merely rest on fallacious opinions. The bipartisan American orthodoxy since 1990’s has led to disastrous

outcomes; the intervention in Iraq, Libya, Ukraine and Syria has led to international instability, wars (unilateral, proxy, and civil), growing terrorism, failed “nation building,” mounting refugee crises, and a new cold war with Russia. Putin may have contributed to it along the way but his actions in his tenure of fourteen years were mostly reactive and not actively aggressive as portrayed by the American media.

Cohen further assesses that Washington’s anti-parity thinking and assertion of America’s pre-eminence in international relations remains a virtually sacred US policy-making axiom. The book examines Washington’s policy toward Moscow, from the disastrous crusade to remaking Russia in America’s image in the 1990s, ongoing expansion of NATO to Russia’s borders, nonreciprocal negotiations known as “selective cooperation,” double-standard conduct abroad, and broken promises to persistent “democracy-promotion” intrusions into Russia’s domestic politics and the recent Ukrainian crisis. Washington has perceived post-Soviet Russia as a defeated and thus lesser nation. Cohen advises the US policy makers that when there is military parity between Washington and Moscow, as during the preceding cold war and now again, it is imperative to cooperate and not to ostracize.

Cohen further evaluates on how US “core” interests would “need” Russia’s cooperation in many vital ways that includes:

- avoiding nuclear war;
- preventing a new and more dangerous arms race;
- guarding against the proliferation of weapons and materials of mass destruction;
- coping with international terrorists;
- achieving lasting peace in Syria and elsewhere in the Middle East;
- fostering prosperity and stability in Europe;
- promoting better relations with the Islamic world; and
- avoiding a generation-long confrontation with a formidable new alliance that already includes Russia, China, Iran, and other non-NATO countries.

The book explores how Russia has played a crucial role in the nuclear-weapons agreement with Iran; its behind-the-scenes part today, in attempts to resolve the conflict with North Korea; its potential as a deciding partner in bringing peace to Syria; and the role it is likely to play when the United States finally decides to leave Afghanistan. Russia can be a vital peacemaker. Cohen has recommended this based on how diplomatic breakthroughs, involving Syria and Ukraine that might end or substantially reduce the US-Russian proxy wars

in those countries and thus the new cold war itself. This two-front détente diplomacy represents a fateful opportunity, to be seized or lost as were previous ones. Cohen believes that if given opportunity president Trump with his pro-détente diplomacy could end the cold war. He further examines that the pro-cold war party's refusal to engage Trump on these vital issues would be detrimental to US national security and to American democracy. Such perception of Cohen about Russia which is also prevalent in his previous books has earned him the image of the most controversial Russia expert in America.

The book further discusses on a *myopia* that has been constantly perpetuated by the American media that Russia is “isolated from the international community.” According to Cohen, this is an Anglo-American conceit. Russia has expanded its multi-dimensional relations with non-Western countries such as China, Iran, India, and other BRIC nations where most of the world's territory, people, resources, and growing markets are located. Russia's turning away from the West, and its “pivot to China,” is now widely acknowledged and embraced by many Moscow policy thinkers. As for these countries, Russia is an eagerly sought out partner. The book further examines that Russia is not a real threat to the US national security, but in actuality, they are:

- Russiagate allegations which is a threat created more by American elites and not by Russia;
- Demonization of Putin by mainstream American media who are not well informed;
- ISIS and other international terrorist organizations who are in pursuit of radioactive materials;
- Proliferation of states with nuclear weapons;
- Climate change.

Both Trump and Putin have insisted that the real threat is not Syrian President Assad but the Islamic State and other terrorists. “Putin's Kremlin” had destroyed the vicious Islamic State's grip on significant parts of Syria, for which it has still got no credit in Washington. According to Cohen, any actual Russian threats today are primarily of the West's own making; mostly reactions to US-led policies in recent years. Further Cohen has suggested a US–Russian coalition against the Islamic State and its terrorist accomplices, which could possibly diminish the new cold war. Cohen believes that US does not need a “friend” in the Kremlin, but a national-security partner whose nation's interests are sufficiently mutual for sustained cooperation for détente instead of Cold War.

The book also focuses on the failure of NATO's eastward expansion since 1990's in Balkans and later in Iraq and Libya that has resulted in more military

and political insecurity than security. Cohen describes this as a “pseudosecurity of simmering crises.” The outcomes of NATO wars have bred political-ideological insecurities in Serbia (1999), Iraq (2003), Georgia (2008) and in Afghanistan, (initially NATO’s effort) which is now the longest war in American history. Cohen implies that the only “Russian threats” since the end of the Soviet Union are ones provoked by US-led NATO itself, from Georgia and Ukraine to the Baltic states. The enormous resources devoted to NATO expansion have scarcely contributed anything to resolving real international crises, among them economic problems in Europe that have helped inspire its own secessionist movements; international terrorism in the Middle East and the refugee crisis; the danger of nuclear proliferation, which NATO has abetted by spurring a new nuclear arms race with Russia; and others. As NATO expanded, space for democracy in Russia has diminished. Cohen believes that for the sake of international security, NATO expansion must end. Cohen reiterates the accusation that Putin wants to “destabilize Western democracies,” from America to Europe. Cohen clarifies that Putin needs a stable and prosperous EU as an essential Russian trading partner as he needs security guarantees for Russia.

Furthermore, the book tries to uncover the Ukrainian neo-Nazism, that has been ignored by the U.S. political-media establishment, including prominent American Jews and their organizations due to unqualified support for Kiev. Cohen states that media outlets have reported on corruption in Ukraine, but not on the frequent manifestations of neo-fascism.

Cohen mentions in his book that American media, today, are less objective on Russia, less balanced, more conformist, and scarcely less ideological than when they covered Soviet Russia during the preceding cold war. The stenographic American media has gone from the fog of cold war to falsification. According to him, media malpractice is now pervasive and the new norm and mainstream media outlets like outlets *New York Times*, *Washington Post*, *CNN*, *Times*, etc.) have played a woeful role in all of this. Cohen further adds that American media establishment continues to enforce their orthodox narrative that Russia is solely to blame for the new cold war. They have failed to offer diversity of opinion and reporting, but “confirmation bias.” Alternative voices rarely appear any longer in the most influential newspapers or on national television or radio.

Cohen’s book has disclosed various facts and figures that have nullified Russiagate’s allegations. Cohen states that for most mainstream media, Russiagate has become a kind of cult journalism, that no counter-evidence or analysis can dent. The book explains that the claims of the American president being compromised by or that he is an agent of the Kremlin lacks persuasive historical evidence or political logic. Russiagaters have even alleged that Russia

“meddled” in the 2016 US presidential election and thus committed “an act of war against America.” According to Cohen, the word “meddle” is both capacious and imprecise as governments have meddled in the elections and interfered in the domestic politics of other states for centuries in one form or another. One such instance cited is the Clinton administration’s highly intrusive political and financial intervention on behalf of Russian President Yeltsin’s reelection campaign in 1996. Cohen has provided an extensive analysis that states that the American media’s fact-free allegations and unbiased reporting and commentary on Russiagate has delegitimized American elections.

Moreover, Cohen speculates that the CIA and FBI have played unsavory roles in Russiagate. Trump-Putin allegations that alarmed cold war hysteria in the American political-media establishment have no facts to support them. To this, Cohen indicates that the CIA has had a long history of leading American presidents into disastrous wars, from the Bay of Pigs and Vietnam to Iraq and Libya. According to him, Russiagate is a ploy to keep the conspiracy theory moving forward toward Trump’s removal from office by whatever means. This is a futile investigation, which generates smoke but no smoking gun is to be found. Cohen believes that such allegations by political and media elites have denounced Trump’s meeting with Putin at the expense of American and international security. Although Cohen’s perspective on US-Russia relations has excluded him from various media outlets, his opinions cannot be completely denied. This is discernible from the fact that Cohen’s assessment was proven correct that Mikhail Gorbachev was a true democrat, which was contrasted in 1980. Further in 1990, Cohen was among the first one to uncover the corrupt policies of Boris Yeltsin that adversely affected Russia.

The book attempts to provide Cohen’s evaluation of how the American media and political elites have misrepresented Russiagate allegations and the new cold war preceded by the Ukrainian crisis. Cohen’s book has raised a controversial debate that has invited a lot of criticism from the media and academic scholars. However, the book is strongly recommended as it gives an alternative outlook based on substantial facts that one may possibly have overlooked. This book should not be perceived as one of the conspired theories, as Cohen suggests, but be read for in-depth understanding of the intertwined relations between American politics and media.